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journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**HISTORY OF THE CATERING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: CHANGES, PLANS AND PRACTICE (LATE XIX - EARLY XX CENTURIES)****Nasirov Bunyod Uralovich***Ph.D., Associate professor of Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan.***ИСТОРИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО ПИТАНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ, ПЛАНЫ И ПРАКТИКА (КОНЕЦ XIX - НАЧАЛО XX ВЕКОВ)****Насиров Бунёд Уралович***Доцент Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.***O'ZBEKISTONDA OVQATLANISH TIZIMI TARIXI: O'ZGARISHLAR, REJALAR VA AMALIYOT (XIX ASR OXIRI-XX ASR BOSHLARI)****Nosirov Bunyod Uralovich***Mirzo Ulugbek nomidagi O'zbekiston milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali dotsenti.***abstract**

In the article, the author describes the changes in the catering system in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the emergence and development of new types of service in the industry, and the reaction of the population to these changes.

аннотация

В статье автор описывает изменения в системе общественного питания в конце 19-го и начале 20-го веков, появление и развитие новых видов обслуживания в отрасли, а также реакцию населения на эти изменения.

annotatsiya

Maqolada muallif 19-asr oxiri-20-asr boshlarida ovqatlanish tizimidagi o'zgarishlar, sohada yangi xizmat turlarining paydo bo'lishi va rivojlanishi,

aholining ushbu o'zgarishlarga munosabati tasvirlangan.

Keywords:

teahouse, restaurant, buffet, catering, service, Soviet government, sector, population.

Ключевые слова:

чайхана, ресторан, шведский стол, общественное питание, сервис, советское правительство, сектор, население.

Kalit so'zlar:

choyxona, restoran, bufet, ovqatlanish, xizmat ko'rsatish, Sovet hukumati, sektor, aholi.

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Introduction

Social life cannot be imagined without the service sector. In fact, social-household infrastructures, while performing socio-economic tasks, contribute to the efficient use of people's free time. Also, this sector has an important place in the life of the population.

In this regard, the provision of services for the vital activities of the population in the countries of the world and the socio-economic development of the country is of

great importance. At the same time, the share of the service sector in the gross domestic product of foreign countries is high, including in Monaco - 95.1%, in Luxembourg - 86.0%, in Malta - 80.6%, in the USA - 79.6%, in Cyprus - 78.3%. , in France – 77.6 percent, in Belgium – 76.1 percent, in Greece – 75.7 percent and in Great Britain – 74.5 percent [1].

In the period of fundamental reforms implemented in the society, it is important to look into the past, to study the history of generations and the daily life of the population. In this regard, during the years of the Soviet government, issues such as the daily lifestyle of the population, the functioning and problems of existing social and household infrastructures, and the attitude of the population have a special place.

Research methodology

It should be noted that the term "communal meal" also means a large number of meals prepared outside the household. The practice of countries such as Western Europe, the USA and Japan shows that investments in public catering establishments pay off quickly. In foreign countries, semi-automated or fully automated kitchens and cafes, as well as cafeterias that prepare food such as "fast food", grill bars, and restaurants with a buffet in the form of a "buffet table" and similar dining areas are very popular [2].

Figure 1.

In addition to environmental factors, quality nutrition is also very important for the growth and development of the population. Eating according to age, sex, work activity and health status is not only for young people, but also for the working ability and health of the elderly. shows positive repair [3].

Therefore, the culture of cooking and eating, which is one of the components of the traditional culture of life, is a reflection of spiritual life. Because food and drinks

prepared from various blessings are the main source of the human body and are of great importance in its physical and spiritual development [4].

In the history of Uzbekistan, catering establishments have been going for a long time, and the following should be recognized in the emergence of their modern forms. Even today, the teahouses, which are still visited by many people, were built in the olden days in the beautiful places of rabots, bazaars, guzars and neighborhoods, in which, in addition to tea and bread, various sweets and fruit cakes were sold, and food was also prepared. Teahouses also served as a place for foreigners and travelers to spend the night [5].

It is worth saying that teahouses beloved by the Uzbek people since ancient times, have a unique role in improving the living conditions of the population. Consequently, at the end of the 19th century, together with teahouses, changes in the provision of services in this regard took place, and new-look establishments began to operate.

Local historians of the Russian Empire, B. Khanikov, P. I. Nebolsin and I. Gayer, commented on the traditional dishes of the local population. In particular, B. Khanikov published information on fruit and vegetables grown in the territory of the Bukhara

Figure 2. Tea room on the market [6]

During the period of the Russian Empire, new-style buffets, hotels (with dining facilities) and restaurants began to become the traditional eating places of the population in their daily lives. Of course, the appeal of the local population to them was relatively low. For example, in 1894, Konstantin Gorgaridze from Samarkand appealed to the Governor of Turkestan to build a restaurant selling strong drinks for

the local population, informed that there is an "Orisam" restaurant in the new Bukhara and acknowledged that only independent people can visit it [7]. In our opinion, this situation is caused by the fact that the local population was not used to visit, and secondly, the existing prices had also had an effect.

Results

From that period, attention was paid to the construction of factories for the production of alcoholic beverages, the organization of warehouses, and the establishment of restaurants selling various alcoholic drinks. For example, in the same period, 2 breweries, 1 vodka production factory, 1 beer and wine warehouse, 1 Russian grape wine dealer, 3 pubs and 1 cafeteria were established in the territory of New Margilan, while in Kokon there were 4 Russian grape wine dealers, 1 cafeteria, in Andijan there were 5 Russian grape wine dealers, and 1 liquor store. Of course, at that time, these indicators existed in the Samarkand region, as well as in the Jizzakh and Katta-Kurgan regions, although they were relatively small [8]. The number of cafeterias and drinking establishments belonging to the Russian food industry was analyzed in relation to the Russian population in the city during that period [9]. However, issues such as the development of various kitchens and teahouses of the local population were neglected.

A collection of information on teahouses dating back to 1904 is presented in the collection volume addressed to the Police Department of the part of the archive fund where Russians live in the city of Tashkent. In particular, an appeal will be sent to the military governor of Syrdarya region by Lieutenant General Matsievsky. In it, Matsievskiy states that he could not find enough grounds to close the tea shop belonging to Janarboeva [10]. Why was it necessary to close the teahouse, which was working?

In general, by the end of the 19th century, restaurants such as "Rivera", "Paris", "Shimal" (Samarkand), "Regina", "Buffa", "Anona" (Tashkent) were working in Central Asia, serving only the upper class [11].

Figure 3.

In the 30s of the 20th century, red tea houses were established, lectures on various topics were organized, newspapers and magazines were read on a large scale. That is to say, the Soviet authorities skillfully tried to use teahouses, which had been traditional for them for a long time, to inculcate their ideas in the population. As a result of rapid growth of red teahouses, in 1937 their number in the republic was 3437. At the same time, there were -700 in Bukhara region. In one year, 4176 lectures and speeches were given in red teahouses in Bukhara region. As of January 1, 1939, the number of red tea houses in Uzbekistan was 4073 [12].

In the Soviet era, the general catering system included factory-kitchen, preparation, canteens, home kitchens, restaurants, teahouses, cafes, canteens and buffets. Some of them served the population in places of work and study, and a certain part of the expenses for preparing food would be borne by those organizations, institutions and educational institutions [13].

As an example of changes in the network in the mass development of public catering, the organization of highly mechanized institutions, providing them with ready-made and semi-cooked products, canned and frozen ready-made meals became important [14].

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that in that period transformational processes took place in the public catering system, which became important in the daily life of the population, and new forms of service were created [15]. Instead, over the years, a lot of attention had been paid to the establishment of catering establishments in

Figure 4. Dining room of the dining room of the Syrdarya district consumer society 1956 [16].

residential areas, and later in places of work and study, and new forms of service had been established. However, despite the introduction of new types of

services, it was important that there was a high demand for teahouses during a long history.

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